

Title

Effects of Crevice Corrosion on Epoxy Performance in Marine Environments

Authors

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Abstract

Corrosion is one of the leading challenges for engineers and researchers working in the marine environment. As a result, work is constantly underway to combat this process and determine new ways to improve our ability to utilize marine resources. This research assesses the viability of different epoxy adhesives for marine applications and investigates the effects of crevice corrosion on the bond strength and performance of these epoxies when used to bond stainless steel surfaces. Plexus and Araldite epoxies were chosen for this assessment and metal-metal lap shear (MMLS) specimens of 316 stainless steel were prepared according to ASTM D1002-10 standards. To thoroughly investigate these adhesives, these specimens were created using different surface preparation methods made distinct by the presence or absence of IPA and primer, and the variation of sandblasting material between silica and walnut sands. Multiple samples were created for each epoxy and subsequent preparation methods to acquire a broader dataset for proper analysis. Additionally, extra samples were created for two of the epoxies using 2205 stainless steel to determine if the epoxy performance varies with different alloys. Once complete, the specimens were mounted vertically in an open crate and deployed into the intercoastal waterway at Florida Atlantic University's SeaTech campus. The samples were fully submerged, suspended from a small floating barge, and checked periodically for visual progress assessment. After 3 months, half the samples were retrieved for testing, with the rest following at the 6-month mark. Each sample was dried and mounted to an MTS load frame for testing under static loading conditions at 3mm/min. Displacement and force data were recorded and ultimate shear stresses were calculated. The data for each sample was compared to a dry, uncorroded control. Upon completion of testing, any remaining epoxy product was stripped from the surface of the steel and a qualitative (visual) assessment of crevice corrosion within the bond layers was performed. This observation is to be compared to the quantitative test results and a final analysis of the gathered data will be executed establishing the viability of the tested epoxies for use in the marine environment.